

Study the Structure and Properties of Antibacterial TiO₂/HAP Coating onto Ti Alloy Using Electrophoretic Deposition Technique for Biomedical Application

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Abstract:

In the present study, single layer, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and TiO₂/HAP nano-particles coatings were fabricated by electrophoretic deposition on titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V. As a result of accidents, diseases and other causes, efforts and research are continued to reach results closest.

The damaged that occur to some of them in the living of the organism in general and the humanbeing in particular, this can be done throughout the existing the implantation of medical minerals, ligaments of bones, teeth and other parts that compensate. Through science, opportunities and experiments have been provided to obtain satisfactory results in terms of the biocompatibility of titanium alloy

Ti-6Al-4V implants and their alloys, which are classified as one of the best biocompatible materials within vivo tissues. This study aims to increase improve this alloy antibacterial properties by coating the surface with a bio ceramic (TiO₂ and TiO₂/HAP) nano-powders. were made on titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V substrate using an electrophoretic deposition (EPD) technique, charged particles suspended in ethanol at a concentration of 50 g/L, for each powder with ideal conditions of 20V and a deposition time of (4 min). The surface characteristics of coated substrates, such as micro-hardness, surface roughness and wettability antibacterial test were evaluated and compared to that of the uncoatedsubstrates. The results showed that the EPD is a promising technique to create a bio coating on titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V substrate with outstanding structure and properties for biomedical applications. The results demonstrated that the coated sample under coating conditions (20V, 4min) which is close to the ratio found in living bone. The results also of the wettability test showed that the contact angle of the deposited paint is 5.9 degrees, and this positive result is useful for biomedical applications and proved that the coating is hydrophilic.

Keywords: *Structure, antibacterial TiO₂, Electrophoretic, Technique.*

Introduction

Occasionally, accidents happen and crucial parts of our bodies are in required of replacement or mending. Other times, as increasingly seen on a

global scale, the same parts are worn out by a lifelong service to its host. Thanks to the dedicated work of countless medical professionals, scientists and engineers. However,

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biocompatible materials, surgical procedures, medicines, and antibiotics have been developed to successfully mend this, significantly improving the quality of life for millions of people. Nevertheless, the complexity of our biological system and its intricate symbiotic relationship with bacteria can still cause materials, surgical procedures or treatments to fail. These challenges, along with longer life expectancies and higher demands from society, have resulted in a pressing need for improvements and the development of new advanced products and technologies.

Biomedical material is any substance that has been engineered to interact with biological systems for a medical purpose, which may be therapeutic (i.e., to treat, augment, repair, or replace malfunctioning tissue in the body) or diagnostic. Among the various types of biomedical materials, metallic materials are the most widely used because of their high load-supporting capacity, desirable qualities of wear and friction, and acceptable biocompatibility.

Titanium, titanium alloys and Ti-6Al-4V are the most frequently used metallic materials for biomedical applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, high fatigue resistance, and good biocompatibility.

Regrettably, metallic implants suffer from different deficiencies, such as low/high corrosion resistance, releasing toxic ions, and low biocompatibility. Microbial infections in the biomedical implants pose a grave threat in modern medicine. A biofilm infection stays a prime reason of failure in biomaterial implants. Thus, the application of the antimicrobial agents into implant surfaces to prohibit implant-associated infection has attracted lots of surveillance. To find a solution to this matter, many surface modification methods are proposed that coating techniques are among the most paramount ones. Each of these techniques elucidates different capabilities and one has to choose a coating method based on their needs and implementations. Among these techniques, the most popular are sol-gel, high-velocity

suspension spray, and electrochemical coating processes.

Biomaterials

Biomaterial is acquainted as "A nondrug substance proper for listing in systems which increment or replace the function of bodily tissues or organs".

Biomaterials are broadly classified into three major categories according to biocompatibility are as follows: bioinert, bioactive, and bioresorbable.

Bioinert: These are the materials which when placed has minimal interaction with the tissue surrounding it, thus leading to osteogenesis. Some of the examples are stainless steel, titanium, zirconium, alumina, and ultra-high-molecular-weight polyethylene

Bioactive: These are the materials once placed inside the oral cavity react with the hard tissues as well as the soft tissues. Examples are synthetic hydroxyapatite, glass ceramic, and bio glass.

Bioresorbable: These materials on placement begin to resorb which get slowly replaced with bone. Examples are tricalcium phosphate, polylactic–polyglycolic acid copolymers, calcium oxide, calcium carbonate, and gypsum.

Thus, bio inert and bioactive materials are called as "osteoconductive" materials as they have the ability to act as "scaffolds" for bone deposition on its surfaces.

Biomaterials can also be classified based on chemical composition into metals, ceramics, and polymers as follows:

- Metals: titanium, titanium alloys, stainless steel, cobalt chromium alloys, gold alloys, and tantalum.
- Ceramics: alumina, hydroxyapatite, beta-tricalcium phosphate, carbon, carbon/silicon, bioglass, zirconia, and zirconia-toughened alumina.
- Polymers: polymethyl methacrylate, polytetrafluoroethylene, polyethylene, polysulfone, polyurethane, and polyether ether

ketone.

Application of biomaterials in human body as implants is very common nowadays. In Figure (1.1), the locations of implants in different areas of human body are shown. As illustrated, biomaterials can be used in many locations in human body such as shoulders, hips, joints, bones, dental implants, etc. Once these biomaterials are planted in the human body, they will be subjected to human body fluid environment. The living body fluid is corrosive for metallic biomaterials. As a result, biomaterials degradation occurs ultimately unless they are covered with appropriate coatings that could prevent corrosion.

Figure 1. Application of Biomaterials as Implants in Different Areas of Human Body

General View

This chapter covers a general view about biotic titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V and coating of TiO₂/HAP bio-ceramic used in metallic

implants. There will be a focus on the functionally graded materials (FGMs) properties and their applications in various fields, also the difference between them and traditional composites, as well as coating techniques. This chapter will cover up the literature relevant to this study, several neoteric experimental and theoretical investigations about biomaterials on the one hand and electrophoretic deposition, on the other in general. The world people median age is growing; so the demand for bone substitute metallic implant will increase. Property features like as relatively low elastic modulus, high fatigue strength, and the osseointegration made titanium an appropriate choice for bone implant industrialization. However, weak surface characteristics such as depressed hardness, scant wear and scratch resistance deemed as its blind spot. Therefore research and development on titanium implants was concentrated on surface engineering. The using of bioactive hydroxyapatite (HAp) as a coating the titanium implant surface, gets better the surface characteristics. As well as accelerates the induction and conduction of the osteoblast cells, which in turn reduce the implant fixation time in the host tissue. In spite of the common utilize of HAp coating, its permanency has permanently been a challenge due to a contradiction between ceramic coating and metallic substrate characteristics, especially coefficient of thermal expansion which outcomes in residual stresses. Insufficient coating coherency and indigent adhesion to the substrate lead to the coating delamination and detachment under loading in the physiological environment and inflammatory responses arise. Therefore, the coated implant not only will have utility over non-coated ones but also has more destructive consequences, so in spite of coating procedure, permanency and durability of HAp coating deemed as a general demand. The TiO₂ layer is a favorable option as an intermediate layer between the HAp coating and the titanium substrate, because of the high mechanical integrity of TiO₂ with HAp and its chemical similarity to both HAp and titanium. Moreover, the TiO₂ coating has superior tribological properties, anti-bacterial activity, and its biocompatibility has been proven by in-vitro and in-vivo biological tests.

Types of Biomaterials

A biomaterial is any material, natural or man-made, that comprises whole or part of a living structure or biomedical device which performs, augments, or replaces a natural function. These biomaterials are specifically designed by utilizing the classes of materials: polymers, ceramics, metals and composite materials. Most of the biomaterials available today are developed either singly or in combination of the materials of these classes. These classes of materials have different atomic arrangement which present the diversified structural, physical, chemical, and mechanical properties and hence offer various alternative applications in the body.

The classes of the materials are illustrated in the following sections.

Polymers

Polymers are the convenient materials for biomedical applications and used as cardiovascular devices for replacement and proliferation of various soft tissues. There are a large number of polymeric materials that have been used as implants. The current applications of them include cardiac valves, artificial hearts, vascular grafts, breast prosthesis, dental materials, fixtures of extracorporeal oxygenators, dialysis and plasmapheresis systems, coating materials for medical products, surgical materials, tissue adhesives, etc. The composition, structure, and organization of constituent macromolecules specify the properties of polymers. Further, the versatility in diverse application requires the production of polymers that are pre-pared in different structures and compositions with appropriate physicochemical, interfacial, and biomimetic properties to meet specific purpose.

Ceramics

Ceramics are another class of materials used for designing biomaterials. The use of ceramics is motivated by their inertness in the body, their assay formability into a variety of shapes and porosities, high compressive strength, and excellent wear characteristics. Ceramics are used

as parts of the musculoskeletal system, hip prostheses, artificial knees, bone grafts, dental and orthopedic implants, orbital and middle ear implants, cardiac valves, and coatings to improve the biocompatibility of

metallic implants. Though ceramics are utilized for designing biomaterials, yet they have been preferred less commonly than either metals or polymers. Applications of ceramics in some cases are severely restricted due to brittleness and poor tensile strength. However, bioceramics of phosphates are widely used to manufacture ideal biomaterials due to their high biocompatibility and bone integration, as well as being the materials that are most similar to the mineral component of the bones. Some of the materials which used in this study are listed below.

Hydroxyapatite (HAp)

Hydroxyapatite (HAp) has been used as a bioactive component in dental and orthopedic fields for many decades. HA belongs to the calcium phosphates group possessing the following chemical formula of $\text{Ca}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, which can be found in nature chemically synthesized. It seems to be the most suitable ceramic material for hard tissue replacement implants from the view of biocompatibility. The methodology behind the wide use of HAp is because of its similar composition to bone. Therefore, HAp ceramics don't exhibit any cytotoxic effects. Around 70% of human bone and up to 90% of human dental enamel is made up of calcium phosphate. Since HAp closely resembles the chemical structure of bone, rapid integration and bone regeneration will be obtained by using HAp. To overcome the brittle character of bioceramics, HAp is usually coated on the surface of titanium implants as load-bearing prosthesis.

Titania (TiO_2)

Three phases of oxide titanium or titania in atmosphere (air) are anatase (a metastable mineral form of titanium dioxide), rutile and brookite. Pure Rutile is a desirable phase in clinical applications due to the high corrosion protection of metallic implants, a large single

crystal can be easily obtained, high biocompatibility and usually stated to be the thermodynamically most stable form of TiO₂. Anatase phase also has bioactivity properties. Anatase gradually transforms to rutile depending on temperature that has bioactivity properties. There are only small differences in Gibbs free energy between anatase, brookite and rutile (4-20 kJ/mol) meaning that the metastable polymer phase is almost as stable as rutile at normal pressures and temperatures.

Titanium dioxide combines excellent resistance to corrosion and superior biocompatibility with photocatalytic activity. These properties make TiO₂ an ideal

biomaterial with various ubiquitous applications in pharmaceuticals, pigments and cosmetics, and it has attracted particularly wide usage in the biomedical field as an integrating agent for implant-bone tissues. These ideal properties are due to its physio-chemical properties, including inertness, thermal stability, and an ability to assume various polymorphic forms: anatase, rutile, brookite, and oxygen deficient α -Ti₃O₅. The application of TiO₂ anatase coatings on the Ti-implant surface is one of the best ways to enhance the interactions between the material and the biological environment at the interface. Lorenzetti, reported that an anatase layer significantly reduced bacterial attachment with respect to the amorphous titania layer, without adverse effects on the cell metabolic activity. Implant surfaces are mainly modified to increase osseous integration into the alveolar bone; recently however, implant surfaces are also modified to reduce biofilm formation after exposure to the oral cavity. Innovative implant materials or surface modifications with reduced adhesion properties or even with antibacterial properties are of pertinent clinical interest. Up to now, monolithic titanium has been the most frequently used base material and gold standard for the construction of implant systems. Titanium is known for its excellent biocompatibility and outstanding mechanical properties. Surface roughness, texture, and wettability are regarded as the most significant surface factors influencing microbial accumulation on implants. Increased surface

roughness on implant surfaces correlates with faster and firmer integration into the surrounding bone. On the other hand, however, most studies indicate a positive correlation between surface roughness and the amount of adhering bacteria.

Wettability is quantified by the CA, which is the angle between the tangent line to a liquid drop's surface at the three phase boundary and the horizontal solid's surface. In principle, the CA can range from 0° to 180°. Surfaces with water CAs lower than 90° are designated as hydrophilic, and those with CAs very close to 0° are superhydrophilic. Surfaces with water CAs above 90° are considered hydrophobic, and those with CAs above 150° are termed superhydrophobic. Most implant surfaces currently in clinical use are hydrophobic, according to findings and those of other groups. However, the range of CAs found on different dental implant surfaces varies widely, from superhydrophobic angles around 150 to superhydrophilic ones of 0. Moreover, it is commonly accepted that surface topography and surface roughness have a strong influence on the bacterial adhesion.

Biocompatible Coating

The various coatings have been applied for many years in medicine to improve the properties of the interface between implants and tissues, which determine the biocompatibility and healing time. In past years, the reviews on such functional coatings for dental implantology, biocompatible coatings for bone implants, ion substituted hydroxyapatite thin films, titanium implants polymeric coatings, ceramic coatings for osteoporotic bones, and pulse laser deposited animal-originated calcium coatings can be found. The coatings for biological applications, called biocoatings, maybe made of metals, polymers, ceramics, and bioglasses, or can be composite coatings, co-deposited, or formed layer-by-layer (hybrid or sandwich coatings). They may be formed by various techniques such as direct electrocathodic deposition (ECD), pulse electrocathodic deposition plasma electrochemical oxidation (PEO) called also

micro-arc oxidation (MAO) in calcium, and phosphorus-containing phosphate solutions, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), plasma vapor deposition (PVD), magnetron sputtering, pulsed laser deposition, and many others.

Coating material	Medical applications	Advantages
Nitrides (TiN, ZrN, NbN, TiAlN) Oxynitrides (TiON, ZrON, TiSiON)	Dental implants Fracture fixation devices Metal components of joint end prostheses	High corrosion resistance High adhesion on the metallic surfaces Good friction Coefficient
Carbon-based coatings (DLC, CN, a-C, carbides, carbonitrides)	Artificial heart valves Orthopedic fixation devices Artificial ligaments and Tendons	Low friction coefficient and wear rate High biocompatibility with blood
Calcium phosphates, bioglass	Percutaneous devices Spinal implants Maxillofacial reconstruction Skull plates	High osseointegration Capability
Oxides (TiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , ZrO ₂)	Dental implants Devices for increasing alveolar area Maxillofacial reconstruction Ophthalmic implants	High corrosion resistance Good regenerative Capability

Figure 2. Bioceramic Coatings with Different Coating Materials Used for Medical Applications in the Human Body

They may coat the solid or porous substrates. Comparing all the existent coatings, the bioceramic coatings appear to be the best choice for metallic implants. The advantages of various

types of bioceramic coatings besides their applications are shown in Figure 2. The research on the biocompatibility improvement by both bioactive and bioinert functionalization coatings deposited on metallic implant surfaces has become one of the hottest topics in biomaterials. The new trend in medical application is to use the implants with antibacterial properties along with good mechanical and physical-chemical properties and high bond bonding.

Materials Used

This chapter deals with materials, used equipments, and preparation method of samples for coating processes. It also contains several tests such as: microhardness, corrosion and the microstructure. Metallography was carried out by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Figure (3.1) shows the block diagram of procedures for experimental part.

Metal Substrate

The substrate metal used in this work was titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V. Specimens of (20mm diameter×10mm height) were used as the substrates. The chemical analysis of this alloy was conducted in general company for examination and rehabilitation engineering Baghdad. Details composition (weight %) are shown in a Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical Compositions for Titanium Alloy Ti-6Al-4V

Element	(V)	(Al)	(Fe)	(C)	(Ti)
Standard AISI	3.5-4.5	5.5-6.75	0-0.3	0-0.08	Balance
W%	4	6	0.002	0.04	Balance

Coating materials high purity (>95%) hydroxyapatite powder and titanium dioxide (anatase TiO₂) powder, with particle size respectively were used for suspension preparation in absolute ethanol 100% purity,

distilled water and dilute ethanol 70% as medium of EPD process. The materials which were used during this research in electrophoretic coating process, as shown in Figure 3 as follows:

Figure 3. Shows Materials, Powder Used in this Work

TiO₂

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles, also called ultrafine titanium dioxide or nanocrystalline titanium dioxide or microcrystalline titanium dioxide, are particles of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) with diameters (10-30 nm) and (TiO₂, Anatase, Purity +99.5%) was used in electrophoretic coating process.

Samples Preparation for Coating Process

The specimen was prepared before coating by:

1. All specimens were grinded and polished using emery paper (SiC paper) No. (180, 220, 320, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1200, 1500 and 2000) respectively. Then samples were washed with distilled water and, then dried by using a dryer of an electrical. A polishing was conducted by diamond paste.
2. Specimens were immersed in acetone for 30 min
3. Before coating, specimens are immersed in solution, electro cleaning include materials (60g/l NaOH ,38g/l NaCO₃ and 30g/l NaPbO₄) for one minute period at 70°C temperature with moving the electrolyte using magnetic stirring with (5 volt) in order to

eliminate the dust and the oil from the metal surface, follow that specimens are washed by distilled water and then dried and after that, it directed immersion in coating solution.

Method

Titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V substrate as cathode, and commercially available titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V as the counter electrode, were immersed in the suspension with a fixed distance of (15 mm). In order for the process to be more accurate, a holder was manufactured to hold the samples and keep the distance between the electrodes constant during the coating process and to facilitate the lifting of samples when changing the suspension, as shown in the Figure 4.

EPD process was performed in a glass beaker, magnetic stirring was employed to maintain the homogeneous dispersion of the particles during the whole EPD process. The system was equipped with a DC power supply to give potential ranging from zero to 60 volt. The voltage can be adjusted

as required to achieve the best deposition. In order to determine the optimal electrophoretic

parameters deposition to be performed at voltage as (20) V and different deposition times (2, 4,6) min from suspension containing (1 g/L)% TiO₂ , 1g/L HAP and (0.5 g/l TiO₂/HAP). The pH of suspension was measured by a pH meter (model PH-100 meter). After that, the coated samples were removed carefully from the EPD cell and dried in air at room temperature for 24 hrs, Firstly, TiO₂ were dispersed in an ultrasonic bath, then the addition of TiO₂ to the coating bath. After preparing the suspensions by adding weight ratios of powder to pure ethanol and determining the optimum conditions, voltage and time deposition were (20V, 2min). TiO₂ layer was deposited on the titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V

substrate. Figure 4 shows the setup of electrophoretic coating process deposition. Figure 5 shows a photo of coating specimens.

Table 2. Operating Conditions for Electrophoretic Bath

<i>Bath composition</i>	<i>Quantity</i>
TiO ₂	1g/l
HAP	1 g/l
Ethanol (ml)	200 ml
<i>Operating conditions</i>	
pH	12
voltage	20V
Time of immersion	4 min

Figure 4. Experimental Setup for Electrophoretic Deposition

Figure 5. Shows the Samples Before and After Coatings

Tests

Carried out the present research for procedure of the upcoming tests for evaluating performance of coating layers. the examination was conducted at the University of Babylon in the department of materials engineering

Metallography Test

Coating Thickness Measurements

A digital coating thickness gage Type (TT260), is used to determine the coating thickness in this work as shown in Figure 6. The device accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$. In this method, measurement is taken in the three places to given averaged thickness for coating specimen.

Figure 6. Coating Thickness Instrument

Figure 7. Scanning Electron Microscopy are Used

Scanning Electron Microscope

SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) are used to study topography of the coating in the MIRA3 TESCAN Company in Babylon University, Iraq. SEM is carried out at different magnifications for electroless layer, as shown in Figure 7.

Phase Identification

XRD was used for phase identification of coating by using (EQUINOX X-3000, by Cu Ka ($\lambda=1.54187\text{\AA}$) radiation. Scanning domain of 2θ (40kV and 30mA) is used, for identification to sample crystal structure before and after heat treatment and the treatment of plasma nitriding operating at a scanning speed of 6° (2θ) per minute. Figure 8 shows the x-ray machine used a type (EQUIN X-3000), in Babylon University, Iraq.

Figure 8. The X-Ray Machine Used (EQUINX-3000)

Mechanical Test

Microhardness Test

Microhardness of the coating layers are measured by using (TH-717 Vickers hardness tester), at the ceramic materials lab. Babylon University. This process was carried out distribution on the coated layer for the TiO_2 and

base metal before and after coating. A load of 25 g was applied for 15 Sec. The three readings are recorded for each specimen coated and for the substrate. Then, the average value was taken.

$$HV = 1.854 \times Pd^2 \quad (1)$$

Where: P= applied load kg, and d= average length of diagonal mm²

Contact Angle Measurement

Table 3. Simulated Body Fluids Used in Electrochemical Contact Angle Measurement

The hydrophobicity or wet-ability of the coated Ti-6Al-4V alloy and uncoated samples were measured using the static contact angle (θ) of droplet on solid surface, which is an important index to quantitatively evaluate the wettability of solid surface, the optical contact angle equipment type CAM 110-O4W which was attached with CCD camera was used to measure contact angle, and the contact angle measurement was taken immediately after the droplet was placed on the solid surface by a 1 μ L pipettor. In individual contact angle measurements between each test liquid and each solid surface, each contact angle was measured 5 times and 10 measurement points were selected. Table (3.3) Simulated body fluids used in electrochemical contact angle measurement. <i>Simulated body fluid</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>Concentration (g/ML)</i>	<i>PH</i>
Ringer's solution	C3H5NaO3 NaCl KCl CaCl2.2H2o(Na+ , k+) HCO3 Cl- Ca++	1.55 3.0 0.15 0.1 (130.3,4)mEq/L 27.7 109.4 2.7	6.5
NaCl 0.9 %	Sodium chloride (NaCl)	9	7

Surface Roughness Test

The value of surface roughness measurement was carried out to the coated samples before and after the heat treatment and treatment of plasma nitriding using a common parameter Ra in μ m. In test of surface roughness calculated a mean of (10) measurements was recorded.

Results

This chapter presents and discusses results that were obtained from the several tests that were conducted throughout this work. These tests included mechanical and electrochemical tests of the examined samples, such as metallography, microhardness, inspection of surface roughness using scanning electron microscope (SEM), optical microscope and x-ray diffraction (XRD).

Microstructure of the Ti-6Al-4V Substrate

Figure 9 illustrates the microstructure of the cast Ti-6Al-4V where the microstructure consisted of equiaxed alpha grains, elongated alpha grains and a network of intergranular beta phase. It is observed that the samples have been etched to reveal the grain boundaries in the microstructure. Pores of different size are irregular but have been rounded. The most common types of features in the microstructure in metallic materials are the boundaries between crystalline grains and /or the boundaries between different solid phases in multiphase alloys.

Figure 9. As-Received Microstructure of Ti-6Al-4V Alloy Showing Elongated α (blue arrow), Equiaxed α (red arrow) and Intergranular β (black arrow) Using Different Magnification

Surface Morphology

Figure (10 a ,b, c and d) shows the morphology of the surface of the coated sample in which the smooth microstructure of TiO₂ and the TiO₂ /HAP sample can be observed in Figure (4.2 a ,b, c and d) coatings have good interconnection between particles, also shows that the morphology of biocoating, TiO₂ layer and TiO₂ /HAP, that are deposited at the deposition 20V for 4 min represented a smooth, dense (more close packed microstructures), good homogeneity surface with less porous structure, crack- free and uniform coating were achieved,

The rough and porous morphology of the coating surface facilitates the accumulation of nucleations and osseointegration of bone in the formation of bone-producing cells.

a

b

c

d

Figure 10. Images SEM of the Surface Morphology of Biocoatings on Austenitic Ti-6Al-4V Alloy. (a, b), TiO₂ and (c, d) TiO₂/HAP Layer Coating at Different Magnifications

Surface Roughness

Data regarding the roughness of the substrate and plated samples has been illustrated in Table 4. The TiO₂ and TiO₂/HAP coatings has textured surface with higher roughness among samples, nevertheless, without appropriate mechanical strength, high roughness will be unworthy. By surface roughness measurement, the biocoatings is the optimal option among others. It was pointed out that the rapid attachment of the osteoblast cells onto the implant surface can be achieved by increasing the surface roughness, which may provide a substantial improving in contact area with the bone. Roughness acts as a driving force for osseointegration due to the high surface energy of the rough surface as well as the improvement of contact between the bone and implant. On the other hand, higher surface roughness lead to increase bacteria adhesion.

TiO₂ and TiO₂/HAP coatings reduces the brittleness of the coating and the cracks are almost eliminated. TiO₂/HAP has lowest surface roughness than other coatings. Also, the calculated average surface roughness parameters for all coatings are in the micro-metric range.

Table 4. Results of Roughness of Samples Surface

Specimen	Ra (μ)
Substrate	0.7
(TiO ₂) a plated	1.2
TiO ₂ /HAP	2

Coating Thickness

With a digital coating of thickness gage type (TT260 country), which is used to determine coating thickness, the average thickness of TiO₂/HAP coating is determined to be (18μm) on the substrate surface at factor deposition time (t) 4 min. The reason for increasing the coating thickness with increasing deposition time is to give sufficient time for precipitation of the

largest possible number of TiO₂/HAP particles layer on substrate. We note that the thickness of the coating increases with increasing sedimentation.

Microhardness

As is well identified, the biomaterial utilized for long-term implants should possess higher mechanical strength and better biological properties owing to the complex nature of human body environment. Therefore, in this study, the micro-hardness, as one of the mechanical properties required for coated surfaces, is evaluated, and the results of uncoated and coated samples are represented in Table 5. It can be seen from this table that the hardness of uncoated substrate is 80 HV, which is the lowest value compared with that of coated substrates. On the other hand, the average micro-hardness of the TiO₂ coated sample is 144 HV. The values of the Vickers hardness test results are summarized in Table 5. From this Table, it can be concluded that the value of hardness TiO₂ coated large than its substrate. This can be attributed to the fact, that the presence of TiO₂ particles coating layer will improve the physical reliability between the substrate and coating layer to produce a higher bonding between the particles, and this lead to a marked increase in the hardness of the layer. Furthermore, the coating with coherent layer, significant bonding strength and lower amount of porosity provides higher hardness. Figure 11 shows the surface microhardness of the samples

Table 5. Experimental Data Micro-Hardness of the Coated and Uncoated Sample

Specimen	Vickers Hardness (HV)
Substrate	80
(TiO ₂) a plated(20V,4 min)	144
(HAP) a plated(20V,4 min)	134
(TiO ₂ /HAP) a plated(20V,4 min)	200

Figure 11. Microhardness Results of as-Plated Samples

Wettability

The surface of non-coated Ti-6Al-4V alloy surface sample has a higher aqueous contact

angle of 75.2° and indicates a less hydrophilic surface compared to the coated samples that presents a contact angle of test values as illustrated in Table 6.

Table 6. Contact Angle (θ°) of Ti-6Al-4V and Coated Samples

Sample	Ti-6Al-4V alloy		TiO ₂	
	Ringer's solution	NaCl 0.9 %	Ringer's solution	NaCl 0.9 %
Contact angle θ (deg)	68.5°	75.2°	22.7°	5.9°

The reduced contact angle may be attributed to the effect of surface texture (surface roughness) as shown in Figure 12 phase (TiO₂ (anatase)) in the coatings as these phase provide synergistic effect to make the surface more hydrophilic. These results agreed with that obtained by other

investigators [78, 79]. Figure (4. 5) reveals surface roughness values of uncoated Ti-6Al-4V alloy and electrophoreses depositing coatings. The results of previous research indicate that the high surface wettability and surface roughness at the micron scale were for the synergistic effect of reduction on cell adhesion and growth.

Figure 12. Effect of Surface Roughness on Wettability

Figure 13. Photometric Quantification of Contact Angle θ° Bound to the Different Experimental Coating Surfaces

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction examination was conducted in the Ministry of Science and Technology to find out the type of Ti-6Al-4V alloy were examined

for the identification of the crystalline phase. Through the XRD diagram showing the type of Ti-6Al-4V alloy in the following Figure 14.

Figure 14. XRD Patterns of Ti-6Al-4V Alloy

Figure 15. Patterns XRD for Plated Sample (TiO₂) and TiO₂/HAP

Conclusions

In the current study, the TiO₂ biocoatings has been deposited on the surface of medical

Ti6Al4V alloy successfully by using EPD process for biomedical applications. The effect of coating layer on mechanical and chemical properties of biocoatings TiO₂ and TiO₂/HAP

coating was investigated. In view of the test results, the following conclusions can be presented.

Main findings from the results and discussion are summarized as follows:

1. The biocoatings TiO₂ coatings were successfully fabricated on Ti6Al4V substrates by electrophoretic deposition after choosing the optimal conditions for coating.
2. The morphology of biocoatings was homogenous and crack-free when coating with the optimum condition at 20 V for 4 min.
3. Layer of TiO₂ and TiO₂/HAP improved the average surface micro-hardness by progressing the coating integrity.
4. The incorporation of titanium deposited provides excellent adhesion to the substrates and may prevent implant loosening, which are highly desirable traits for bio implants, and the results of the examination of the proved this.
5. The obtained coatings thus can be successfully used to change the surface of Ti6Al4V alloy implants to improve their biological properties and antibacterial performance.
6. Average layer thickness of TiO₂/HAP electroless coating is (18 µm) formed on the substrate surface.

Recommendations for Future work

1. Using other materials as substrate in the coating process such Ti-6Al-4V alloy.
2. Studying the effect of variation of EPD process bath composition and operating conditions used for the deposition of coating.
3. Studying the effect of varying operating conditions of plasma nitriding as using a gas mixture of nitrogen, hydrogen and C₂H₂ or using argon/CH₄ flow ratio on layer coating.
4. Studying experimentally and numerically the corrosion behavior of composite biocoatings HAP/TiO₂ on Ti-6Al-4V alloy implant, but in vivo.

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